

1 **Hydroxysteroid metabolism activation during lineage specification in human ES cells.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here identification of
9 hydroxysteroid metabolic pathways important for lineage commitment in embryonic stem cells of the
10 human embryo.

11 Citations

12 1. Rantakari, P., Lagerbohm, H., Kaimainen, M., Suomela, J.P., Strauss, L., Sainio, K., Pakarinen, P.
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